

EFFECT OF PHOSPHORUS AND MULCHING ON THE GROWTH AND YIELD OF GROUNDNUT (*Arachis hypogaea* L.) VARIETIES IN THE NORTHERN GUINEA SAVANNA ALFISOL OF NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study on groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.) performance under different rates of phosphorus and mulching in the Northern Guinea savannas ecological zone of Nigeria addresses challenges of low soil fertility and harsh climatic conditions. Groundnut, an important crop in Nigeria, is limited by phosphorus deficiency and soil moisture stress in the savannas. Field trials were conducted at the Irrigation Research Farms of the Institute for Agricultural Research, Samaru and Nuhu Bamalli Polytechnic Saye, in the dry season of 2022 to evaluate two varieties of groundnut (SAMNUT-24 and SAMNUT-25), three

phosphorus rates (0, 30 and 60 kgP⁻¹₂O₅/ha), and three mulch materials (no mulch, sawdust and dry grass). Treatments were laid out in a randomised complete block design with three replications. Results showed SAMNUT-24 excelled in branches, canopy spread and shoots dry weight, while SAMNUT-25 produced higher pod yield and harvest index. Applying 60 kgP⁻¹₂O₅/ha improved leaves, pod yield and harvest index, while sawdust enhanced leaf number and canopy spread. Both varieties performed well under irrigation. SAMNUT-24 and SAMNUT-25 with 60 kgPOha⁻¹₂₅ and dry grass mulch is recommended for farmers.

Identifying optimal combinations of phosphorus and mulching can enhance groundnut yield and sustainability. Further research is needed to explore phosphorus rates with

Keywords: Number of branches, canopy spread, shoots dry weight, harvest index, mulch, phosphorus, groundnut variety

INTRODUCTION

Groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.) is a leguminous oilseed crop cultivated in the semi-arid and subtropical regions of the world. It is grown in nearly 100 countries across six continents, typically between 40°N and 40°S of the equator, covering an area of approximately 24.6 million hectares with a production of 41.3 million tonnes and a productivity of 1,676 kg/ha in 2012. The

leading groundnut-producing countries include China, India, Nigeria, the USA, and Sudan (USDA, 2022). In 2020, global groundnut production reached 54 million tonnes, representing an 8% increase over 2019. China contributed 34% of global production, followed by India with 19%, and other significant producers including Nigeria (8%), the USA (5%), and Sudan (5%) (FAOSTAT, 2020).

Groundnut is predominantly cultivated as a smallholder crop in the semi-arid tropics under rain-fed conditions. It is an essential crop in many countries, particularly in Sub-

Saharan Africa, where it serves as a valuable source of essential nutrients, cooking oil (48%-50%), and essential vitamins and minerals. It also provides a vital feed resource for livestock, especially during the dry season when fresh fodder is scarce. This contributes to additional income for farmers during the off-season, when the demand for fodder is high. Moreover, groundnut remains a sustainable crop as it improves soil productivity through nitrogen fixation and enhances soil fertility through nitrogen fixation and improves soil productivity. (Witcombe and Tiemann, 2022).

Despite its significance, groundnut productivity in many African countries remains low due to a combination of factors such as erratic rainfall, reliance on rain-fed farming practices with limited mechanization, use of low-yielding varieties, continued cultivation of marginal land, inadequate adoption of improved groundnut varieties, and limited extension services (Anonymous, 2015). A major barrier to improving groundnut production is the lack of adoption of improved varieties suited to the different agro-ecological zones. The use of improved varieties has been shown to significantly increase yields. Coupled with the adoption of sound agronomic practices, these efforts could lead to further yield improvements. Increased yields and better returns on investment would incentivise smallholder farmers to invest in productivity-enhancing technologies.

Phosphorus plays a crucial role in various physiological processes, including cell division, flowering, crop maturation, root development, and nodulation. It is vital for crop maturation, root growth, photosynthesis, and nitrogen fixation.

Given the challenges in procuring additional water resources, farmers must adopt water-use efficiency practices. One such practice is the use of mulches, which have been shown to enhance water absorption and retention in the soil (Schneider and Mathers, 1970). Mulches help regulate soil temperature, reduce evaporation, and suppress weed growth. Improved groundnut varieties and improved groundnut varieties in the Nigerian savanna. (Ramakrishna *et al.*, 2006). Given these challenges, the objectives of this study are to assess the effects of phosphorus and mulch application on the performance of improved groundnut varieties in the Nigerian savanna.

Experimental Site

Field trials were conducted in two locations during the 2022 dry season at the research farms of the Institute for Agricultural Research, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, Samaru (11^o, 11'N; 7^o38 E) and 686 m above sea level, and at the Nuhu, Bamalli Polytechnic Saye (11^o03'N, 07^o67' E), in the Northern Guinea Savanna of Nigeria (Kowal and Knabe, 1972).

Treatments, Experimental Design, and Plot Size The treatments consisted of three mulching materials (sawdust mulch, dry grass mulch

and no mulch), two varieties of groundnut (SAMNUT-24 and SAMNUT-25) and three rates of phosphorus (0, 30 and 60 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹). The treatments were factorially combined and laid out in a randomized complete block design and replicated three times. A sunken bed was prepared in which the gross and net plot sizes were 3.0m x 4.0m (12m)² and 2.0m x 3.0m (6m)², respectively.

was later thinned to one seedling per stand. Seeds will be dressed in Dress force (a.i. Imidacloprid 20%+Metlaxyl 20%+Lebuconazole 2% WS) @10g/4kg prior to sowing. Water was applied prior to sowing once every five days for four weeks and was later increased to twice a week for six weeks, and subsequently reduced to once a week until maturity/harvest. Hoe weeding was carried out in the controlled plots at 3 and 6 weeks after

Soil Sampling and Analysis

Soil samples will be taken randomly from sowing (WAS), and by hand pulling in the ten points each in the experimental sites at a mulched treated plots at 4 and 7 WAS.

Harvesting was done when the crop reached physiological maturity and the chemical properties of the soil have a practical laboratory

Description of Varieties
 SAMNUT-24: This is an early maturing variety (80-90 days). The good pods were detached from the haulms and allowed to dry for several days under the sun. It has high oil content (53%). Anonymous (2021)
 SAMNUT-25: This is an early maturing variety (80-90 days), with high oil content (53%), highly resistant to rosette and moderately resistant to early leaf spot and late leaf spot disease and with high oil content of (51.5%). Anonymous, (2021)

Cultural Practices

Two weeks prior to land preparation, glyphosate will be applied at the rate of 0.5 kg a.i. ha⁻¹ in both locations. The fields will be harrowed, marked out into plots and levelled into basins. This was done for all the three replications. The rice straw was shredded, weighed 6kg for each plot and used as straw mulch. It was evenly spread on the plots as per treatments. The Polythene mulch was purchased from a renowned supplier in Kano State. It is transparent and was pre-punched at 25 by 20 cm inter- and intra-row spacing respectively and used in plots as per treatment.

Three (3) seeds per hole were sown, which

Data collection commenced from 3WAS. Five plants were randomly tagged within the net plot and growth parameters were measured from the tagged plants at 3, 6, 9, and 12 WAS. Assessment of growth characters was done at 3, 6, 9 and 12WAS, and in each plot, plants will be randomly selected, and the following parameters will be measured. Plant height was measured using a meter rule from the ground level to the terminal leaflet at 3, 6, 9 and 12 WAS and recorded. The number of leaves was counted per plant from the five tagged plants from each plot and the average per plot will be determined and recorded. Canopy spread will be measured by taking the diameter of the open canopy using a meter rule and the mean obtained will be recorded on per plot basis.

Assessment of yield components was done at harvest Pod yield hectare⁻¹ (kg) The weighed pod per plot was extrapolated to per hectare basis and recorded as pod yield hectare⁻¹. Harvest index The ratio of the dry pod yield to the total dry matter was calculated at harvest using the formula:-

$$HI = \frac{\text{pod yield from sample}}{\text{Total dry matter of sample}} \times 100$$

Statistical Analysis

Data collected was subjected to statistical analysis of variance (ANOVA) as described by Snedecor and Cochran (1967). The differences between treatment means was compared using Duncan Multiple Range test (DMRT) (Duncan, 1955).

RESULTS Soil Physical and Chemical Properties of the Experimental Sites

Soil samples from the two experimental sites (Samaru and Saye) were loam and sandy loam, respectively (Table 1). The soil of Samaru has moderate level of nitrogen, high level available phosphorus, while organic carbon, calcium, magnesium, potassium, sodium and cation exchange capacity were moderate while pH was

slightly acidic in H₂O. In Saye the soil has high level of nitrogen and moderate level of available phosphorus and organic carbon, low level of calcium, magnesium, potassium and sodium contents, while pH is slightly acidic in H₂O and strongly acidic in CaCl₂.

Plant Height (cm)

Table 2 shows the plant height of groundnut varieties as influenced by phosphorus rates and mulching materials during 2022 dry season. At 3WAS in Samaru, significantly taller plants were observed for SAMNUT-24. A similar trend was observed for all the other sampling periods at both locations, with the exception of 3WAS and 9WAS at Saye, although the differences were not significant. Increase in phosphorus fertilizer had no significant effect on the plant height at both locations during the sampling periods. Mulching materials had significant effect on the plant height of groundnut varieties at 3 and 6WAS in Samaru and at 3, 6 and 9WAS at Saye. In Samaru, at 3 WAS using dry grass mulch led to significantly taller plants than using the sawdust mulch. At 6 WAS, using the dry grass straw led to significantly taller plants than the control but was statistically similar to using the sawdust mulch. In Saye, using both the dry grass and sawdust mulch led to significantly taller plants than the control at 3 WAS, while the sawdust mulch led to significantly taller plants than the dry grass mulch and the control at 6 and 9 WAS. Highly significant interaction between phosphorus and mulching materials was

observed at 3WAS in Samaru. Application of 30 kgP₂O₅ha with dry grass resulted in the tallest plant which was statistically similar to control with dry grass (Table 3).

Table 1: Soil Physical and Chemical Properties of the Experimental Sites for 0 – 30cm during the 2022 dry season at Samaru and Saye

	Samaru	Saye
Physical properties		
Particle Size Distribution (gkg ⁻¹)		
Clay	140 400	130 310
Silt	460 Sandy	610 Sandy
Sand	loam	loam
Textural class		
Chemical properties		
pH (H ₂ O) 1:2:5	6.21	6.01
pH 0.01m CaCl ₂	5.61	5.68
Total N gkg ⁻¹	1.10	1.18
Available P mgkg ⁻¹	9.78	6.84
Organic carbon gkg ⁻¹	10.1	11.5
Exchangeable bases (cmolkg ⁻¹)	0	6
Calcium	2.8	2.5
Magnesium	5	8
Potassium	0.6	0.5
Sodium	1	8
Exchangeable Acidity	0.1	0.1
CEC cmolkg ⁻¹	1	5
	0.1	0.2
	6	0
	0.1	0.2

Table 3: Interaction of phosphorus and mulching materials on plant height of groundnut in Samaru at 3WAS during 2022 dry season

Mulch	Phosphorus(kgha ⁻¹)	
	0	30
Nomulch	5.26 ^b	5.45 ^b
Sawdust	6.83 ^b	5.43 ^b
Drygrass	8.56 ^a	9.18 ^a
SE±	0.485	

Means followed by different letter in a column are significantly different at 5% level using DMRT.
WAS= Weeks after sowing

Table 2: Plant height of groundnut varieties as influenced by phosphorus rates and mulching materials in Samaru and Saye at 3, 6, 9 and 12 WAS during 2022 dry season

Treatment	Plant height (cm)							
	Samaru (WAS)				Saye(WAS)			
	3	6	9	12	3	6	9	12
Variety (V)								
SAMNUT-24	6.98 ^a	13.56	30.26	43.54	5.99	14.99	28.51	41.15
SAMNUT-25	6.19 ^b	13.41	29.73	42.10	6.42	14.65	28.62	40.62
SE±	0.229	0.549	0.758	1.024	0.286	0.432	0.812	1.462
Phosphorus (P)(kgPQha ⁻¹)								
0	6.89	12.59	29.46	41.57	6.27	14.31	28.03	39.18
30	6.69	13.69	29.88	43.47	5.82	14.39	27.77	40.26
60	6.20	14.17	30.63	43.38	6.53	15.77	29.88	43.21
SE±	0.279	0.673	0.928	1.255	0.350	0.531	0.994	1.790
Mulch Type (M)								
No mulch	5.47 ^b	12.21 ^b	29.77	41.80	4.66 ^b	14.21 ^b	27.12 ^b	38.13
Sawdust	6.17 ^b	13.88 ^{ab}	29.46	42.32	7.32 ^a	16.47 ^a	31.83 ^a	42.31
Dry grass	8.12 ^a	14.36 ^a	30.74	44.29	6.63 ^a	13.79 ^b	26.74 ^b	42.21
SE±	0.279	0.673	0.928	1.255	0.350	0.531	0.994	1.790
Interaction								
VxP	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
VxM	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
PxM	**	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
VxPxM	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS

Means in a column of any set of treatment followed by different letter are significantly different at 5% level using DMRT. WAS= Weeks after sowing. **= Significant at 1% NS = Not significant

Number of leaves plant⁻¹

Number of leaves of groundnut varieties as influenced by phosphorus rate and mulching at Samaru and Saye in 3, 6, 9 and 12 WAS is presented in (Table 4). At both locations, variety did not differ significantly on the number of leaf throughout the sampling periods. Phosphorus application rate did not significantly increase number of leaves throughout the sampling periods at Samaru while significant ($P < 0.05$) increase of number of leaves at sampling periods of 6 and 9 WAS where control

treatments and higher rate of 60 kg ha⁻¹ were

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statistically at par with 30 kg P₂O₅·ha significantly ($P < 0.05$) produced lower number of leaves. Mulching had a significant ($P < 0.05$) effect on both

locations. In Samaru, sawdust mulch recorded the highest number of leaves, which was statistically similar with no-mulch at 3WAS. However, no-mulch recorded significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher number of leaves at 6WAS which was followed by dry grass mulch. At 12WAS, zero mulch gave the highest number of leaves, trailed by sawdust. In Saye, sawdust mulch had the highest number of leaves at 3WAS which was statistically similar with dry grass mulch. At 6WAS, no mulch had the highest number of leaves in which sawdust and dry grass mulch were statistically similar. However, no mulch and sawdust are statistically similar, having higher number of leaves than dry grass mulch at 9 WAS.

Table 4: Number of leaves of groundnut varieties as influenced by phosphorus and mulching materials in Samaru and Saye at 3, 6, 9 and 12 WAS during 2022 dry season

Treatment	Number of leaves							
	Samaru				Saye			
	3WAS	6WAS	9 WAS	12WAS	3WAS	6WAS	9WAS	12WAS
Variety (V)								
SAMNUT-24	6.36	18.16	39.89	61.26	8.55	20.73	35.03	59.98
SAMNUT-25	6.23	17.77	37.02	59.44	9.28	20.50	37.33	59.28
SE±	0.261	0.894	1.852	2.157	0.469	0.671	1.271	2.151
Phosphorus (P) (kgP ⁻¹ ·0 ₅ ·ha)								
0	6.62	17.79	38.56	59.38	9.47	20.60 ^{ab}	39.18 ^a	59.36
30	6.21	19.10	40.14	61.87	8.46	19.25 ^b	33.56 ^b	59.81
60	6.10	17.02	36.66	59.79	8.82	22.00 ^a	35.83 ^{ab}	59.73
SE±	0.319	1.095	2.269	2.642	0.575	0.822	1.557	2.634
Mulch Type (M)								
No mulch	6.67 ^a	21.87 ^a	41.12	64.89 ^a	8.32 ^b	23.21 ^a	39.45 ^a	63.74
Sawdust	7.06 ^a	15.16 ^b	35.99	59.42 ^{ab}	10.26 ^a	18.79 ^b	35.00 ^{ab}	59.26
Dry grass	5.16 ^b	16.87 ^b	38.24	56.72 ^b	8.17 ^b	19.86 ^b	34.11 ^b	55.90
SE±	0.319	1.095	2.269	2.642	0.575	0.822	1.557	2.634
Interaction								
VxP	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
VxM	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
PxM	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
VxPxM	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS

Means in a column of any set of treatment followed by different letter(s) are significantly different at 5% level using DMRT. WAS= Weeks after sowing. * = significant at 5% NS = Not significant

Canopy Spread

Table 5 presents the canopy spread of groundnut as influenced by varieties, phosphorus rates and mulching materials in Samaru and Saye during 2022 dry season. The effect of phosphorus was highly variable and significant ($P < 0.05$) in Samaru at 6WAS while there was no significant effect of phosphorus on the canopy spread at Saye. 0 kgP₀ ha⁻¹ at 3WAS produced the widest canopy. While, at 6WAS widest canopy was observed with application of 30 kgP₀ ha⁻¹. Significant ($P < 0.05$) effect of mulch was observed at

3WAS in Samaru, while there was statistical similarity in the subsequent weeks. At 3WAS sawdust mulch had the widest canopy spread which was followed by no mulch, followed by dry grass mulch. In Saye, significant ($P < 0.05$) differences in canopy spread due to mulch were observed at 12 WAS, where no mulch was observed with wider canopy than that of dry grass mulch which was at par with that of sawdust mulch. No significant interactions were observed between variety and phosphorus in both locations.

Table 5: Canopy spread of groundnut varieties as influenced by phosphorus rates and mulching materials in Samaru and Saye at 3, 6, 9 and 12 WAS during 2022 dry season

Treatment Variety (V)	Canopy spread (cm)							
	Samaru				Saye			
	3WAS	6 WAS	9 WAS	12 WAS	3WAS	6WAS	9WAS	12WA
SAMNUT-24	9.92	17.05	33.42	42.49	9.27	17.65	26.21	40.21
SAMNUT-25	9.71	17.74	32.73	40.30	9.57	17.47	25.06	40.27
SE±	0.249	0.519	1.194	1.379	0.392	0.507	0.612	1.536
Phosphorus (P) (kgP ₀ ha ⁻¹)								
0	10.33 ^a	17.23 ^{ab}	32.90	40.42	9.38	17.86	25.19	38.55
30	9.87 ^{ab}	18.52 ^a	34.22	42.95	8.84	17.15	25.71	40.43
60	9.24 ^b	16.43 ^b	32.09	40.83	10.05	17.67	26.02	41.73
SE±	0.305	0.636	1.463	1.690	0.480	0.621	0.749	1.882
Mulch Type (M)								
Nomulch	9.83 ^{ab}	18.39	33.68	43.91	9.02	17.97	26.44	44.18 ^a
Sawdust	10.42 ^a	16.91	31.67	40.72	9.99	17.95	25.32	39.36 ^{ab}
Dry grass	9.19 ^b	16.88	33.87	39.57	9.26	16.77	25.16	37.17 ^b
SE±	0.305	0.636	1.463	1.690	0.480	0.621	0.749	1.882
Interaction								
VxP	NS	*	NS	NS	NS	**	NS	NS
VxM	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
PxM	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
VxPxM	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS

Means in a column of any set of treatment followed by different letter(s) are significantly different at 5% level using DMRT. WAS= Weeks after sowing. **= Significant at 1% *= significant at 5%. NS = Not significant

Pod Yield ha⁻¹

The effect of phosphorus rates and mulch on pod yield per hectare of groundnut variety as well as phosphorus had no significant effect in both locations is shown in (Table 6). However, mulch had significant (P=<0.05) effect in Samaru in which dry grass mulch had the highest pod yield,

followed by sawdust mulch. The least pod yield was produced by no mulch during the growing period. In Saye, there was no significant response to the mulch materials throughout the trial. There was no significant interaction of treatments on pod yield at both locations and in all the sampling periods.

Table 6: Pod yield of groundnut varieties as influenced by phosphorus rates and mulching materials in Samaru and Saye during 2022 dry season

Treatment (V)	Variety	Pod yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	
		Samaru	Saye
	SAMNUT-24		
	SAMNUT-25 SE±	1449.1	1649.
	Phosphorus (P)(kgP	1636.4	3
	20 ₅ ha ⁻¹)	121.99	1801.
	0	1520.9	0
	30	1542.2	1683.6
	60	1565.2	1672.8
	SE±	149.41	1839.2
	Mulch type (M)		146.04
	No mulch	1345.9 ^b	1725.7
	Sawdust	1427.0 ^{ab}	1628.3
	Dry grass	1855.4 ^a	1821.6
	SE±	149.41	146.04
	Interaction		
	VxP	NS	NS
	VxM	NS	NS
	PxM	NS	NS
	VxPxM	NS	NS

Means in a column of any set of treatment followed by different letter are significantly different at 5% level using DMRT. NS = Not significant

Harvest index

The harvest index of groundnut as influenced by phosphorus rates and mulching materials in Samaru and Saye during the 2024 dry season is shown in Table 7). The effect of varieties phosphorus and mulch was variable in both locations. SAMNUT-25 had significantly (P=<0.05) higher harvest index than SAMNUT-24 in Samaru, where there was no statistical difference in the harvest index of the varieties in Saye. Application of 60 kgP₂O₅

has significantly (P=<0.05) resulted in highest harvest index at both locations, which was followed by 0 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ Samaru and application of 30 kgP₂O₅ ha⁻¹ Saye. The lowest harvest index was observed at Saye with 0 kgP₂O₅ grass mulch significantly (P=<0.05) resulted in highest harvest index at both locations which was followed by sawdust and zero mulch which were statistically similar at both locations.

Table 7: Performance of groundnut varieties as influenced by phosphorus rates and mulching materials on harvest index in Samaru and Saye during 2022 dry season.

Treatment	Harvest index	
	Samaru	Saye
Variety (V)		
SAMNUT-24	36.06 ^b	34.10
SAMNUT-25	37.42 ^a	35.02
SE±	0.421	0.342
Phosphorus (P)(kgP ₂ O ₅ /ha ¹)		
0	26.58 ^b	25.01 ^c
30	41.16 ^a	38.61 ^b
60	42.48 ^a	40.06 ^a
SE±	0.516	0.419
Mulch type (M)		
No mulch	36.12 ^b	33.81 ^b
Sawdust	35.96 ^b	34.09 ^b
Dry grass	38.13 ^a	35.78 ^a
SE±	0.516	0.419
Interaction		
VxP	NS	NS
VxM	NS	NS
PxM	NS	NS
VxPxM	NS	NS

Means in a column of any set of treatment followed by different letter are significantly different at 5% level using DMRT. **= Significant at 1% NS = Not significant

DISCUSSION The soil textural class groundnut. The general higher growth and features were loam and sandy loam at yield components of groundnut were Samaru and Saye, respectively. Also, the observed in Samaru than Saye. This could be as a result of relatively higher pH of soils at Samaru and Saye respectively be as a result of relatively higher were slightly below the optimum but fall phosphorus content at Samaru compared to within the range required by groundnut Saye. The two groundnut varieties exhibited which is 6.0-6.5 (Chhidda *et al.*, 2006). minimal differences in growth parameters in These physical and chemical characteristics both locations. The minimal differences were ideal for the production and optimum between groundnut varieties could be yield of

attributed to variances in their genetic make-up and interaction with the environment.

Usman, (2015) reported that there exhibit a consistent significant difference in growth characters of groundnut which he attributed to variations in their genetic makeup and gene interaction with environment as well as crop management.

The increase in pod yield with increasing the phosphorus rates observed in this study could be due to the ability of phosphorus to greatly interact between variety development, resulting in favourable soil temperature during pod development stage. This result is in accordance with the findings of Kaur et al. (2014) that mulching had positive and significant effects on the phenological growth and yield parameters of groundnut.

Similarly, the study is in agreement with Mouri *et al.* (2018) who observed high leaf area, number of branches plant⁻¹, pod yield ha⁻¹, and harvest index with application of 60 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹. Kwarihi (2005) reported that very pod yield and harvest index in the soil may be affected significantly by phosphorus and legume root development which in turn affect groundnut nitrogen fixation potential. The increase in growth parameters of groundnut observed with the use of mulch in the field is associated with the availability of macro and micro nutrients during the decomposition of the rice straw mulch. In addition, the favourable soil temperature and soil water under mulch during pod development stage was responsible for higher pod yield and harvest index of observed in this study.

This is in conformity with the report of Ghosh *et al.* (2006) in which favourable soil temperature and soil water under mulch during the pod development stage was the reason for higher pod yield and harvest index of groundnut.

The significant interaction observed among the parameters could be due to the fact that phosphorus helps in the development of more extensive root system and thus enable plants absorb more water and nutrients compared with mulching that increased the water use efficiency of the plants. This in turn could enhance the plant's ability to produce more assimilates which confirm findings of Mouri *et al.*, (2018) who

CONCLUSION

It is concluded that both SAMNUT-24 and SAMNUT-25 are suitable for production under irrigation at both ecologies of the

SAMNUT-25 with application of 60 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ using dry grass mulch should be used by farmers in the northern Guinea savannah. However, there is need for further research on phosphorous rates with new/improved varieties.

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